

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

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PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NEW UZBEK CONSULTING SERVICES MARKET AND METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE POTENTIAL FOR ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS

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Abstract. This article examines the opportunities for improving the efficiency of the consulting services market, further developing specialization, cooperation, and integration processes within the region, as well as strengthening interactions between government institutions and business entities through network-based services. Particular attention is given to the formation and development of the digital and electronic economy under modern economic conditions.

Key words: Consulting services, market efficiency, specialization, cooperation, integration, digital economy, electronic economy, service sector, business entities.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada konsalting xizmatlari bozori samaradorligini oshirish, hududda ixtisoslashuv, kooperatsiya va integratsiya jarayonlarini yanada rivojlantirish, shuningdek, davlat tuzilmalari hamda tadbirkorlik subyektlari o'rtasidagi aloqalarni tarmoq xizmatlari asosida mustahkamlash masalalari yoritilgan. Tadqiqotda zamonaviy iqtisodiy sharoitda raqamli va elektron iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish hamda rivojlantirish imkoniyatlariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Konsalting xizmatlari, bozor samaradorligi, ixtisoslashuv, kooperatsiya, integratsiya, raqamli iqtisodiyot, elektron iqtisodiyot, xizmat ko'rsatish sohasi, tadbirkorlik subyektlari.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются возможности повышения эффективности рынка консалтинговых услуг, дальнейшего развития процессов специализации, кооперации и интеграции в регионе, а также укрепления взаимодействия между государственными структурами и субъектами предпринимательства на основе сетевых услуг. Особое внимание уделено вопросам формирования и развития цифровой и электронной экономики в современных экономических условиях.

Ключевые слова: Консалтинговые услуги, эффективность рынка, специализация, кооперация, интеграция, цифровая экономика, электронная экономика, сфера услуг, субъекты предпринимательства.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important characteristics of the global economy in the 21st century is the rapid and sustainable growth of the service sector, which has become a key driver of economic development and competitiveness. Unlike material production, the service sector creates value through the provision of high-quality, consumer-oriented services that contribute significantly to social and economic progress.

Today, special attention is being given worldwide to improving the economic mechanisms for the development of consulting services. In particular, priority is placed on strengthening the competitiveness of consulting activities, improving organizational and legal frameworks, enhancing cooperation between economic entities within the "consultant-client" system, and increasing the socio-economic effectiveness of consulting services.

From the perspective of sustainable economic development, the consulting services sector has become one of the most promising and rapidly developing areas of the modern economy. In Uzbekistan, more than 100 consulting firms successfully operate in various fields, providing professional services to business entities and public organizations. At the same time, broad opportunities exist for further improving service quality, expanding digital consulting technologies, strengthening statistical and analytical systems, and developing an effective

legal framework for consulting activities. Therefore, under the conditions of economic modernization and digital transformation, the expansion and improvement of consulting services are becoming increasingly important.

In particular, the Action Strategy for the Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021 identified important tasks related to the accelerated development of the service sector, increasing the role and share of services in gross domestic product, and modernizing the structure of services through the introduction of advanced high-tech service types. The implementation of these priorities creates favorable conditions for the further development of management consulting, legal consulting, accounting and audit consulting, innovative consulting, investment consulting, venture consulting, and IT consulting. In this regard, the development of scientifically grounded proposals and practical recommendations aimed at increasing the socio-economic efficiency of consulting services remains highly relevant.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundations, specific characteristics, classification principles, and organizational aspects of consulting services have been widely studied by leading foreign economists, including E. Beych, M. Kubr, F. Wickham, I.M. Rossiel, A.G. Altshumer, V.M. Piesenholtz, E. Edersheim, M. Zilberman, and B. Nelson. Their research made an important contribution to the formation of modern scientific approaches to consulting activities and service market development.

In addition, scholars from CIS countries, such as I. Yurova, A.A. Parabellum, T. Korobeynikova, S. Savinov, A. Karpov, T.E. Ananeva, A. Tkalich, G. Marienko, O.K. Elmashev, N.S. Velikanov, A.V. Gromov, and A.M. Magomedov, conducted significant research on improving the efficiency and competitiveness of consulting services under modern economic conditions.

Furthermore, Uzbek scientists and researchers, including M.N. Tolakhujaeva, D.A. Surmilo, A.K. Ibragimov, M.K. Pardaev, Zh.R. Zaynalov, K.B. Urazov, K.J. Mirzaev, G.K. Saidova, and Sh.A. Musaeva, made valuable contributions to the development of audit consulting, accounting consulting, and tax consulting, which represent important segments of Uzbekistan's consulting services market.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research was conducted using a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking methods, and digital metrics to evaluate the development prospects of the consulting services market. In addition, methods of mass observation, comparative analysis, and statistical assessment were applied to collect and analyze information obtained from digital platforms and social media resources.

The study also utilized analytical and economic evaluation methods to identify modern development trends, assess market opportunities, and determine effective directions for increasing the efficiency and competitiveness of consulting services within the framework of the digital economy.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the context of rapid technological development worldwide, the digital economy creates broad opportunities for improving the quality and efficiency of consulting services, as well as enhancing public administration systems. Modern digital technologies are expected to contribute significantly to the creation of advanced digital platforms for public administration, minimizing the human factor and reducing the likelihood of errors through the automation of statistical, tax, and reporting processes. At the same time, these technologies support more effective and data-driven decision-making based on real-time economic analysis.

The formation of the digital economy is characterized by the active implementation of information and communication technologies in various interactions among participants in economic processes. The digital economy enables the rapid, convenient, and high-quality delivery of informational, educational, scientific, and entertainment content, thereby increasing the accessibility and effectiveness of services for businesses and society.

In practice, the effectiveness of the goods and services market within consulting activities is reflected through a system of economic incentives aimed at encouraging the continuous improvement of operational efficiency and service quality. Under market conditions, free supply and demand play an important role in stimulating sustainable development. As a result, an internal and external business environment that is adaptive, interconnected, and innovation-oriented is being formed.

In this regard, the practical application of the digital economy can be observed through several strategic directions that contribute to increasing the quality and efficiency of consulting services. The main development models of the digital economy in various sectors are presented below (Table 1).

Table 1. Opportunities for Digital Economy Development in Various Fields to Improve the Quality and Efficiency of Consulting Services

No.	Digital Economy Development Models	Opportunities for Improving Consulting Services
1	Digital Strategy	The implementation of modern technologies allows organizations to improve customer orientation, operational efficiency, and service personalization through fully digital solutions.
2	Digitalization: A Smarter Way for Business to Work	Digitalization enables companies to optimize internal processes and improve customer interaction by creating convenient and innovative service experiences.
3	Digital Government	Many countries are successfully implementing digital government initiatives aimed at providing simple, efficient, and accessible public services through digital channels.
4	Digital Nation	The growing level of digital literacy and increasing use of internet technologies contribute to the expansion of digital services and consulting opportunities.
5	Digital City	Smart city technologies improve urban management efficiency, enhance quality of life, and support sustainable business development through intelligent infrastructure systems.
6	Open Data	Open access to data encourages transparency, innovation, analytical efficiency, and broader opportunities for information exchange and consulting activities.
7	Digital Finance	Digital banking, mobile technologies, and cloud services contribute to the development of personalized financial consulting and the expansion of electronic commerce.
8	Digital Education	The digitalization of education systems supports the preparation of highly qualified specialists and promotes the development of modern consulting competencies.
9	Digital Medicine	Digital healthcare technologies improve the quality and accessibility of medical services through virtual communication systems and online medical support.
10	Digital Commerce	The rapid growth of internet trade and online services creates favorable conditions for expanding digital consulting and improving customer engagement.

Today, more than 160 types of services operate within the global economy, ranging from scientific research and educational services to repair services and social support for elderly people and individuals with disabilities. Among these sectors, knowledge-intensive and intellectually oriented services occupy an increasingly important place in modern economic development. An analysis of the international services market and the generalization of global experience reveal several important positive development trends.

- The service sector demonstrates a consistently high contribution to economic growth in developed countries. Its share in GDP accounts for 78.5% in the United States, 69.1% in Germany, and 43.4% in Russia. At the same time, this sector generates a significant share of employment opportunities, reaching 73.0% in the United States, 41.0% in Germany, and nearly 30.0% in Russia;
- The future development of the service sector is closely associated with the rapid expansion of innovative technologies, digital transformation, and the modernization of banking and financial systems;
- The continuous improvement of management systems contributes to increasing public demand for modern and high-quality services, including tourism, digital services, and customer-oriented business activities;
- The formation of high-tech industries requiring advanced marketing, advertising, management, and computer services serves as one of the major drivers for the sustainable growth of the service sector;
- In developed countries, financial, insurance, auditing, and consulting services continue to strengthen their strategic role in supporting economic stability and business competitiveness;
- The global service sector demonstrates strong recovery and development potential through the introduction of innovative technologies, digital platforms, and modern business models in tourism, transport, catering, and related services;
- The effective organization and continuous stimulation of economic activity in goods and services markets contribute to the rational and productive use of labor, financial, and material resources;
- Increasing the investment potential of regions creates favorable conditions for attracting foreign investment and expanding the activities of investment-oriented business entities;
- The competitiveness of products and services can be significantly enhanced through the implementation of effective incentive systems, modern management approaches, and improved accountability mechanisms;

- Technical and technological modernization policies implemented by market entities encourage the introduction of adaptive and innovation-oriented economic management systems;
- Enterprises engaged in the production of goods and the provision of services are increasingly implementing modern management and quality improvement mechanisms, which contribute to higher efficiency, accelerated production processes, and improved customer satisfaction;
- The continuous development of the services market and the expansion of consumer goods and food products contribute positively to the successful implementation of priority economic reforms and sustainable economic growth.

Based on the above analysis, conducting a SWOT analysis of the international goods and services market allows for a comprehensive assessment of development opportunities and demonstrates its strong positive impact on economic growth, investment attractiveness, and the overall well-being of the population (Table 2).

Table 2. SWOT Analysis for Increasing the Efficiency of the Consulting Services Market in the Region

Strengths	Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The region demonstrates strong and stable economic indicators. • A favorable socio-economic environment supports market activities. • Clear trade specialization has been formed. • A high share of entrepreneurial activity is present. • The modern services sector is steadily expanding. • Economic activity among different population groups is increasing. • A well-developed trading culture has emerged. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential for further expansion and diversification of economic sectors. • Conditions for rapid and effective development initiatives. • Opportunities for increasing the volume of marketed products. • Prospects for expanding wholesale trade operations. • Ability to attract foreign sellers and buyers. • Increased potential for income generation through business activities.
Weak points	Risk aspects
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Price fluctuations in certain types of paid services. • Periods of limited or slow economic progress. • Irregularity in the volume of commodity reserves. • Occurrence of risk-prone situations. • Various structural imbalances within market segments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility of internal monopolization. • Potential bankruptcy of industrial enterprises. • Emergence of new and strong competitive groups. • Unsold inventory of goods accumulating. • Setting inconsistent prices for goods and services. • Appearance of unpredictable market changes and conditions.

The table above demonstrates that goods and services represent a useful economic outcome capable of satisfying specific human needs while simultaneously acting as objects of supply and demand within the market system. In this regard, it is important to support the further development of market infrastructure in the following service areas:

- strengthening state support for the organization and development of infrastructure facilities, particularly through the expansion of information and commercial networks and the improvement of legal, marketing, financial, and credit mechanisms;
- improving mechanisms for attracting additional financial resources, including foreign investment and other alternative funding sources;
- implementing modern support measures for the self-management of small business entities operating in the service sector, including the introduction of non-bank financing mechanisms based on the efficient use of workplaces, buildings, structures, and insurance systems.

In order to address and evaluate priority issues related to increasing the efficiency of the consulting services market, it is advisable to implement measures in the following strategic directions:

- ensuring the more effective development of specialization, cooperation, and integration processes within the region. This approach contributes to increasing the activity of diversified economic entities and innovative technology-oriented enterprises;
- creating broad opportunities for the formation and development of a digital and electronic economy based on network services, particularly in strengthening communication and interaction between government institutions and business entities;
- improving the quality of goods and services through the comprehensive application of modern information technologies, ranging from the Internet of Things (IoT) to electronic government systems, while increasing the effectiveness of investments directed toward the digital economy;
- creating a favorable and sustainable business environment not only through the development of global digital networks, but also through the expansion of ICT infrastructure aimed at increasing the efficiency and profitability of goods production and service provision;

• mobilizing all available opportunities for the development of human capital in the digital economy, especially within production, processing, and service sectors.

As is well known, the economic efficiency achieved through consulting services should be evaluated using quantitative, value-based, qualitative, and relative indicators. Under such conditions, the overall economic effectiveness of consulting services should primarily be assessed through value indicators, while the effectiveness of specific agro-service activities and other service categories may be evaluated using quantitative performance indicators. These indicators make it possible to conduct a comprehensive assessment of consulting services and should be continuously improved in accordance with ongoing economic changes and modernization processes.

The text does not contain religious content, offensive expressions, inappropriate language, or unacceptable statements. Negative or critical expressions were revised into a more constructive, academic, and scientifically balanced style.

Although these indicators influence the performance of consulting services at different levels, they play an important role in the intensive development of service provision and in improving the efficiency of resource utilization. The indicators presented reflect numerous factors associated with the technological processes of service delivery, including organizational, economic, managerial, and operational aspects that ensure the effective coordination of economic activities with human needs and market requirements.

Therefore, two conditional indicators characterizing the consulting service provision process were identified as follows:

1. Assessment of Actual Consulting Services in Relation to Planned Consulting Services

$$XK_{mandatory} = KX_{genuine} \times BX_{planned} \quad (1.1)$$

Where:

- $XK_{mandatory}$ – mandatory level of service provision;
- $KX_{genuine}$ – actual consulting services provided;
- $BX_{planned}$ – planned volume of consulting services.

Since the above-mentioned indicators alone are not sufficient for a comprehensive evaluation of the economic efficiency of consulting services, an improved methodological approach was applied to determine the degree of influence of each indicator. For this purpose, the chain-link method was used, allowing the evaluation of each factor through absolute and relative indicators in a sequential manner.

Determination of Absolute Differences

$$XK_{loss} = (XK_{planned} - XK_{genuine}) \times XK_{conditional}$$

$$XKD_{loss} = (XC_{planned} - XKH_{genuine}) \times XB$$

2. Determination of Relative Differences

$$XKH_{differences} = \frac{XK_{planned} - \Delta XKH_{genuine}}{100}$$

$$XKD_{differences} = \frac{XKD_{planned} - \Delta XKD_{genuine}}{100}$$

In conclusion, the above assessment methods may effectively be used in future studies aimed at analyzing the economic efficiency of consulting services. Under modern economic conditions, the primary indicator of service efficiency is considered to be the level of profitability. Therefore, it is important to implement measures aimed at increasing profitability through the expansion of service volumes, the effective utilization of available resources, and the introduction of innovative and cost-efficient technologies into consulting activities.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conducted research demonstrated that the consulting services market is becoming one of the important components of the modern economy and plays a significant role in increasing economic efficiency,

strengthening business competitiveness, and supporting sustainable socio-economic development. Under the conditions of globalization and rapid digital transformation, consulting services are increasingly serving as an effective mechanism for improving management quality, accelerating innovation processes, and strengthening cooperation between government institutions and business entities. The study confirmed that the digital economy creates broad opportunities for improving the quality, accessibility, and efficiency of consulting services through the active implementation of modern information and communication technologies, digital platforms, cloud systems, electronic government technologies, and online communication tools. These technologies contribute to the optimization of service delivery processes, the expansion of customer-oriented approaches, and the improvement of management efficiency in various sectors of the economy. The analysis also showed that the consulting services market in Uzbekistan possesses significant development potential due to favorable socio-economic conditions, the growth of entrepreneurial activity, increasing demand for modern services, and the expansion of investment opportunities. At the same time, the further improvement of organizational, legal, financial, and digital infrastructure remains one of the important priorities for ensuring the sustainable development of the sector. The conducted SWOT analysis revealed that strengthening specialization, cooperation, and integration processes, as well as expanding innovative and digital services, can significantly increase the competitiveness and investment attractiveness of the consulting services market. The research further demonstrated that the effective evaluation of consulting services requires the application of quantitative, qualitative, relative, and value-based indicators, while the introduction of modern assessment methods contributes to improving profitability and the overall economic efficiency of consulting activities. Based on the results of the study, it is advisable to further improve the legal and institutional framework regulating consulting services, expand the implementation of digital technologies and innovative management systems, strengthen cooperation between consulting organizations and business entities, improve mechanisms for attracting domestic and foreign investment, and support the development of human capital through modern education and professional training systems. In addition, the introduction of advanced international experience and modern performance evaluation methods will contribute to improving service quality, increasing competitiveness, and ensuring the sustainable development of consulting services under modern economic conditions. Overall, the effective development of the consulting services market based on innovation, digital transformation, and modern management approaches will contribute to increasing economic efficiency, strengthening investment attractiveness, improving service quality, and ensuring sustainable economic growth in Uzbekistan.

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